

ON THE CONSTITUTION OF SERPININE, A MINOR ALKALOID OF
RAUWOLFIA SERPENTINA BENTH. *

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From *R. serpentina* Benth. a new alkaloid, serpinine, $C_{20}H_{24}ON_2$, has been isolated in poor yield. Its colour reactions, properties, U. V. and I. R. spectra have been examined. Several degradative experiments have been carried out. From the available experimental data, a hexahydro- β -carboline structure of serpinine has been suggested. It is found to be closely related to ajmaline in properties and constitution.

The occurrence of a new alkaloid, serpinine, as a minor base in the root of Dehra Dun variety of *Rauwolfia serpentina* Benth. was reported earlier by the present author (*Naturwiss.*, 1955, 42, 71). The base has now been isolated in sufficient quantity for studying its properties and chemical constitution, a detailed account of which is presented in this communication.

Serpinine, $C_{20}H_{24}ON_2$, has been isolated from the accumulated mother-liquor of rauwolfine (Bose, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 47). It crystallises from alcohol in glistening rectangular plates which melt at $315-17^\circ$ with simultaneous decomposition and sublimation. Serpinine does not possess any methoxyl group but it contains one N-Me and one C-Me function. It feebly reduces Tollien's reagent and is not soluble in aqueous sodium hydroxide. Serpinine does not produce any characteristic coloration with ferric chloride, but it responds to the following colour reactions with various alkaloidal reagents (Table I).

TABLE I

Reagents.	Colour.	Reagents.	Colour.
1. Conc. H_2SO_4	Nil	5. Ehrlich	Brown
2. Fröhde's	Nil	6. Hopkins-Cole	Slight brown
3. Otto	No characteristic colour	7. Conc. HNO_3	Deep red
4. Keller	Do	8. Ceric sulphate + conc. H_2SO_4	Bright red

These colour reactions indicate the presence of an indoline moiety in the base which has received independent confirmation from the studies of its ultraviolet and infra-red absorption spectra.

* Since submission of this paper, a manuscript on "The Structures of Tetraphyllicine, Ajmalidine and Rauvomitine" has been received from Dr. C. Djerassi of Wayne University, Michigan, U.S.A. The constitution of tetraphyllicine appears to be identical with serpinine.

The U.V. curve of serpinine, which has been studied in ethanol with a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer (Model DU), resembles very closely those of indoline bases, namely, ajmaline (Chatterjee and Bose, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 17) and rauwolfine (Bose, *ibid.*, 1954, 31, 311). It shows $\lambda_{\max}$ at $250m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.97) and $293 m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.51), and $\lambda_{\min}$ at 227 and 272 $m\mu$ respectively. The infra-red spectrum of serpinine, examined in nujol mull with a Baird double-beam spectrophotometer, exhibits absorption bands at 6.25μ (indoline nucleus), 6.84μ (phenyl nucleus), 7.24μ (C-Me), 7.4μ (N-Me) and 13.55μ (*o*-disubstituted phenyl) besides two other bands at 2.85μ (weak) (for -OH group) and at 11.2μ (attributable to an exocyclic double bond). Serpinine, when treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and pyridine, forms a crystalline monotosyl derivative, m.p. 191-92°. The base does not form any oxime and is not changed by sodium borohydride. Upon ozonolysis it forms acetaldehyde, which has been identified as its *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 125-26°. The isolation of acetaldehyde confirms the presence of an exocyclic ethyldene group which is discernible in the I.R. spectrum of the base.

For determining the skeletal structure of the alkaloid, it has been subjected to selenium dehydrogenation at 300°. From the degradation products several uncharacterised indolaceous compounds have been obtained besides Ind-N-methylharman, which has been identified as its picrate, $C_{19}H_{15}O_7N_3$, m.p. 260-61° (decomp.). The isolation of Ind-N-methylharman has induced the author to suggest the following partial structure (I) for serpinine:

Now all *Rauwolfia* alkaloids, partial or total structure of which is known, are at least tetracyclic (II). Serpinine, which belongs to this group of alkaloids, is likely to possess similar fused ring system (III) by analogy.

Further evolution of the structure (V) for serpinine has been possible by the application of Woodward's fission hypothesis (*Nature*, 1948, 162, 155) and the theory

(*Angew. Chem.*, 1956, 68, 13) that he has developed for deducing unambiguously the structure of ajmaline (IV), a companion of serpinine.

As regards the position of the exocyclic ethylidene group in serpinine, it is most probably located at C₁₀ (VI), as in mavacurine (Bickel, Schmidt and Karrer, *Helv. Ch. m. Acta*, 1955, 38, 649), corresponding to the ethyl group in ajmaline.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Isolation of Serpinine.—Crude rauwolfine (20.0 g.), isolated from the alcoholic extract of the roots of *R. serpentina* Benth. of Dehra Dun variety by the process described earlier (Bose, *loc. cit.*, p. 47), was purified by crystallisation from alcohol. The mother-liquor, obtained after separation of the crystals of rauwolfine, was concentrated to a small volume and kept in a frigidaire. After some time it was found that needle-shaped crystals were deposited along with a gummy mass. The crystals, m.p. 305-10° (with decomposition and sublimation) were freed from the adhered gum by washing with alcohol, and collected. The alcoholic filtrate was concentrated and poured into 1% acetic acid solution (100 c.c.) and kept overnight, when a dark brown gummy mass separated. It was filtered off and the filtrate was cooled and basified with ammonium hydroxide. The brownish white flocculent precipitate, thus obtained, was taken up in ether (300 c.c.). The ether extract was washed with water, dried, and on being concentrated, left a brownish semi-solid residue. This was dissolved in alcohol and the concentrated solution was seeded with a crystal obtained beforehand, when fine needles, m.p. 304-10° (with decomposition and sublimation), were deposited. They were mixed with crystals obtained earlier and the whole lot was crystallised thrice from absolute alcohol,

when serpinine crystallised out in glistening rectangular plates, m.p. 315-17° (with simultaneous decomposition and sublimation), yield 0.55 g. [Found (in a sample dried in vacuo over P_2O_5 at 140° for five hours): C, 77.74, 77.85; H, 7.66, 7.70; N, 8.93, 8.98; N.Me, 4.78; C.Me, 4.31; eq. wt. (conductometric titration), 305. $C_{20}H_{24}ON_2$ requires C, 77.91; H, 7.79; N, 9.09; 1N.Me, 4.87; 1C.Me, 4.87 per cent. Eq.wt., 308].—Serpinine is moderately soluble in methanol, ethanol and ethyl acetate and is sparingly soluble in chloroform, benzene and ether. It produces an orange-red precipitate with potassium bismuth iodide and a yellowish white precipitate with potassium mercuri-iodide.

Preparation of Monotosyl Derivative of Serpinine.—A solution of well-dried serpinine (0.05 g.) in dry pyridine (3 c.c.) was added to a solution of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (0.05 g. dissolved in 2 c.c. of dry pyridine) at 0°. The mixture was kept at room temperature for a week and afterwards heated on steam-bath for 4 hours. It was next poured into ice-cold sodium bicarbonate solution (20 c.c.) and extracted with chloroform (60 c.c.). The chloroform extract was washed with water, dried and distilled to leave a solid residue. This was mixed with dry benzene and the benzene distilled off under reduced pressure to remove last traces of pyridine. The residue, thus obtained, was crystallised from alcohol, when crystals of serpinine monotosylate, m.p. 191-92°, were deposited. (Found in a sample dried in vacuo over P_2O_5 at 100° for 4 hours: N, 6.32. $C_{27}H_{30}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 6.06 per cent).

Ozonolysis of Serpinine.—Ozonolysis of serpinine (0.15 g.) was carried out by following the same method as adopted by Karrer in the case of mavacurine and fluorocurine (Bickel, Schmidt and Karrer, *loc. cit.*). The acetaldehyde vapour liberated from the ozonolysis products of serpinine was directly passed into an ice-cold 5% aqueous solution of *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with water and dried. The dry mass was crystallised from aqueous alcohol when yellow needles were obtained, m.p. 125-26°. (Found in a sample dried in vacuo over P_2O_5 at 70° for 4 hours: N, 23.2. Calc. for $C_8H_9O_2N_3$: N, 23.46 per cent). It did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample of acetaldehyde-*p*-nitrophenylhydrazone, when mixed.

Selenium Dehydrogenation of Serpinine at 300°.—A thoroughly powdered mixture of serpinine (0.25 g.) and black selenium (0.25 g.) was taken in a hard glass tube and heated up very quickly to 300° in a metal bath, when a vigorous reaction set in. Heating was continued at 300° for five minutes more. The test tube was next allowed to cool and powdered with fine sand, and the mixture was extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet for 6 hours. The dark benzene extract was filtered through a kieselguhr bed and the clear filtrate was evaporated to leave an oily residue. This on distillation in high vacuum yielded a yellow oil, b.p. 80°-130°/0.01 mm. together with red selenium. The oil was taken up in ether (50 c.c.) and shaken with 5% aqueous hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.) when two fractions, (A) and (B), were obtained. The ether layer (B) containing non-basic products left an oily residue on removal of the solvent. From the faecal odour of the oil and also from its positive Ehrlich and pine chip test, it is suggested that the oily residue is a mixture of several uncharacterised indole compounds. The aqueous acid fraction (A) was cooled in ice and basified with

NaOH and thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether extract (200 c.c.) was washed with water, dried and concentrated to leave a small amount of an oily residue. This on high vacuum sublimation yielded a few drops of a pale yellow oil, b.p. 110° - $120^{\circ}/0.01$ mm. The oil did not solidify on keeping. It was next converted into picrate by mixing its ethereal solution with an ethereal solution of picric acid. The crude picrate was crystallised twice from absolute ethanol in which it was sparingly soluble. The pure picrate melted at $260-61^{\circ}$ with decomposition and did not show any depression in m.p. when mixed with an authentic sample of Ind-N-methyl-harman picrate. [Found (in a sample dried in vacuo over P_2O_5 for 5 hours at 140°): C, 53.54; H, 3.49; N, 16.41. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{12}N_2 \cdot C_6H_3(NO_2)_3OH$: C, 53.65; H, 3.53; N, 16.47 per cent].

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